

Supporting Information Available

Spontaneous nucleation and growth of GaN nanowires: Fundamental role of crystal polarity

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Figure 1. Simulated convergent beam electron diffraction patterns for (0002), (0000), and (0002̄) disks for different thicknesses (20-100 nm).